

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE POLICY OF SUPPORTING YOUTH AND WOMEN'S SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN

Dildorakhon Zulfikarovna Temirova

Researcher of Andizhan State University, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article provides a scientific analysis, based on historical sources, of the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at developing youth and women's sports during the years of independence, the formation of a three-stage sports system, and achievements in the international sports arena. In particular, the study highlights the role of the "Umid Nihollari," "Barkamol Avlod," and "Universiada" sports competitions in fostering the physical development and harmonious upbringing of the younger generation, as well as issues related to the development of children's sports infrastructure, the establishment of sports schools, and the construction of modern sports facilities. Furthermore, the article analyzes the international achievements of Uzbek female athletes, state programs aimed at strengthening women's health, and the processes of promoting a healthy lifestyle through sports. The findings demonstrate that the development of youth and women's sports has become one of the priority directions of state policy in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: youth sports, women's sports, "Umid Nihollari," "Barkamol Avlod," "Universiada," children's sports, healthy generation, sports policy, physical education, international sports competitions.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence, ensuring the physical and spiritual well-being of the younger generation, forming a healthy lifestyle among them, and popularizing sports became a priority direction of state policy. For this purpose, on October 24, 2002, the "Fund for the Development of Children's Sports of Uzbekistan" was established. This fund served to strengthen the material and technical base of children's sports, build modern sports facilities, and widely involve young people in sports. In order to educate young people to be physically healthy, agile, and well-rounded, the physical education system in schools was improved. At the same time, the activities of sports clubs, children's palaces, and mass sports events were expanded. In particular, sports competitions such as "Balli, yigitlar", "Balli, qizlar", "Kuvnoq startlar", "Futbol g'unchalari" and "Oltin kuz" have become important in the development of youth sports[1; P.4.]. During the years of independence, special attention was paid to ensuring that the harvest festival, winter holidays, competitions dedicated to the Navruz holiday, and mass sports holidays became traditions and health events for the school team. In order for the health-improving competitions to have a comprehensive character, it was decided to hold them first between classes, then between schools, districts, and regions, with the final of the competition being held as a republican championship.

LITERATURE REVIEW

During the years of independence, the issue of developing youth and women's sports in Uzbekistan has become one of the scientific areas widely studied by historians, educators, sports scientists, and government organizations. Research is mainly devoted to the issues of forming a healthy generation, developing mass sports, improving the three-tier sports system, and involving women in sports. The main goal of holding the "Sprouts of Hope" sports games in the republic is to educate young people in educational institutions to be physically mature and morally sound, to prepare talented athletes for prestigious competitions, and to popularize sports among the younger generation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

These sports games are a mass sports competition held among students of secondary and youth sports schools in Uzbekistan, and its republican final stages are scheduled to be held once every 3 years [12; 10-p]. The competitions included rhythmic gymnastics, basketball, volleyball, handball, track and field athletics, gymnastics, table tennis, swimming, tennis, and football, as well as mass sports such as chess, belt wrestling, and wrestling. The First Republican Sports Games of Uzbek schoolchildren "Sprouts of Hope" were held in Fergana region in 2002. Many of the young people who have improved their skills in the "Sprouts of Hope" competitions, which are an integral part of the three-stage system, have achieved great achievements in international arenas. While 11 sports were included in the "Sprouts of Hope" sports competitions held in the region this year, in 2015, these competitions in Khorezm were held in a total of 17 sports [13; 9-p]. On May 14-20, 2018, the events to award the winners and prize-winners of the final stage of the "Sprouts of Hope-2018" sports competitions were held in Tashkent as a "Youth and Sports Festival". During the events, a total of 10,444 athletes who won the regional stage in 21 sports were awarded with diplomas and souvenirs [14; 123-p]. A total of more than 63,000 schoolchildren participated in these sports events. The team from Chilanzor district won the championship and was awarded the Presidential Prize with a car "Damas". Representatives of Yunusobod district took second place, and athletes from Mirabod district took third place. The Republican final stages of the three-stage sports competitions for schoolchildren and students were traditionally held. Starting in 2004, it was agreed that the republican final stages of these sports competitions would be held once every three years. Such organized sports competitions served to further popularize sports among the country's youth, strengthen their health and ensure their well-being. Regular sports have had a positive impact on the physical condition and health of many young people in the country. For example, in 2005-2011, the number of absolutely healthy children increased from 52.7% to 62.9% across the republic, while the number of children suffering from chronic diseases decreased sharply [15; p.12]. Young people achieved great success at the "Universiade" competitions organized for university and institute students. It was largely a symbolic continuation of the "Sprouts of Hope" and "Perfect Generation" competitions. At this higher level of the youth sports system, competitions were initially held in 9 sports, but by this time the number of sports in it had reached 15. Students compete in basketball, volleyball, wrestling, belt wrestling, judo, track and field, tennis, table tennis, football, handball, chess, and swimming. These sports competitions have become increasingly popular in the country every year.

Young athletes actively participate not only in local sports competitions, but also in international competitions. In particular, since 1999, Uzbek students have been participating in the World Universiade [16; 2-p]. Uzbek judokas first participated in the World Universiade in Spain in 1999, where A. Bagdasarov won the silver medal at the first Universiade. This victory continued at the World Universiade in Beijing in 2001, where the country's athletes won 5 medals, including 1 gold, 2 silver and 2 bronze medals. The winner of the World University Games was E. Akbarov, the second places were taken by M. Kalikulov and A. Tangriev, and the third places were taken by M. Sokolov and A. Tangriev. Summing up the results, the Uzbek national team took an honorable third place among the 67 participating countries. The team was trained for these competitions by coaches A. A. Istomin and S. D. Murodasilov, who served in Uzbekistan [17; B.18]. At the 2003 World Universiade in Daegu, South Korea, A. Tangriev and E. Akbarov won gold medals in judo, M. Khalikulov won silver, and A. Amanmurodova won bronze medals. [18; 23-p] At the 2005 World Universiade in Izmir, Turkey, D. Mansurov won gold in freestyle wrestling. At the 2007 World Universiade in Bangkok, Thailand, Kh. Nabiev won a gold medal in judo [15; p.14]. At the same time, at the 2015 XXVIII World Universiade in Gwangju, Korea, D. Shokin, a member of the 37-member Uzbek national team, won a gold

medal in taekwondo (WTF). The athlete won a gold medal at the 2014 Asian Championships in Tashkent[19] and a silver medal at the 17th Asian Games in Incheon, South Korea. He won the world championship in his weight category at the World Championships in Chelyabinsk, Russia, from May 12 to 18 of the same year. Representatives of the countries participated in the Special Olympics World Summer Games, which took place in Los Angeles, USA, from July 25 to August 2, 2015. 7,000 young athletes from 170 countries participated in the Special Olympics Games. 20 athletes from the national team of Uzbekistan were able to participate, and it was sponsored by the You Are Not Alone Foundation. The Uzbek Gymnastics Federation led the athletes' preparation for the competition. Uzbek athletes competed in 6 sports: rhythmic and artistic gymnastics, swimming, table tennis, badminton, and athletics. They won 37 medals, including 10 gold, 13 silver, and 14 bronze.[20] Torabek Tirkashev won the gold medal in the Greco-Roman wrestling event at the World Junior Freestyle, Greco-Roman and Women's Wrestling Championships held in Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina) from 25 to 30 August 2015.[21] The 17-year-old athlete, originally from Nukus, also won a bronze medal at the Asian Championships in India in June of this year. At the Asian Youth Wrestling Championship held in Taipei, China on September 6-8 of this year, Uzbek young wrestlers won a total of 8 gold, 5 silver, and 3 bronze medals, taking first place in the overall team standings [22]. About 200 athletes from 10 countries participated in this championship, and gold medals were awarded to Khusniddin Karshiboev, Shahboz Nurmatov, Furkat Marufjanov, Shahrom Akhadov, Beknazar Toraqulov, Rozimurod Mukhimov, and Shohrukh Pirimkulov.

In fact, at the 2019 World Universiade, the winners of the games were awarded large cash prizes of \$10,000, silver medalists \$5,000, and bronze medalists \$2.5 thousand.[24] To summarize, the winners and prize-winners of the XXX World Summer Universiade are Sultanov Humayun Agzamovich - tennis (gold and silver), Fayziev Sanjar Azamat oglu - tennis (gold), Pulatov Niyoz Sergeevich - taekwondo (silver), Khurramov Mukhammadkarim Shokir oglu - judo (bronze), Toraeov Hikmatullo Doston oglu - judo (bronze), Keldiyorova Diyora Bakhtiyor kizi - judo in (bronze), Bobonov Davlat Husniddin oglu - in judo (bronze) [4; P.97.]. Thanks to the honor of independence, a wide path was opened for sportswomen to travel to foreign countries. Such processes served to enrich the Uzbek national culture. In particular, female athletes such as S. Burkhankhodjaeva (tennis) and Yu. Khamroqulova (chess) have become world sports stars. Based on the decrees of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1993, 1996, 1999, 2002) and numerous relevant resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, significant progress has been made in improving women's health, socio-material support, and the provision of regular medical services to them various events were of great historical importance [25; 12-p]. It is worth noting that it has become customary to provide medical assistance to physically weak or sick women on a regular basis. It is worth emphasizing that the sports that are becoming popular in the country are, first of all, inextricably linked with the physical well-being of women and their ability to raise healthy children. At the same time, physical fitness is one of the most important factors in the upbringing of young people, and these aspects quickly entered all families, especially newly formed young families. Taking into account the national characteristics of the republic, a special set of exercises for women and girls, sports with simplified technical rules were developed and the process of their implementation began. In this regard, lectures on physical health of women and girls were organized through television, radio and the media by expert scientists, doctors, and especially in the villages. In addition, measures to develop physical education and sports for women and girls were developed in cooperation with women's committees and sports organizations. Uzbekistan is one of the leading countries in the world in creating favorable conditions for women and protecting motherhood among 125 countries. In the world ranking, the country is among the 10 countries that pay the most attention to maternal and child health [26; 23-p]. As a result of measures being taken to improve the country's population's genetic makeup, the average life expectancy of women will increase from

66 to 73.5 years. It is worth noting that maternal and infant mortality in the republic will decrease by almost 3 times[15; p.43].

Resolution No. 242 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 5, 2002 "On measures to improve medical culture in the family, strengthen women's health, and implement priority directions for the birth and upbringing of a healthy generation" established sports competitions among girls for the "For a Healthy Generation" award, including tennis and rhythmic gymnastics. The task of organizing and holding was assigned to state bodies. Since 2005, under the direct supervision of the State Women's Committee, sports festivals "Gymnastics for All" and sports games under the slogans "Father, Mother and I are a Sports Family" and "Healthy Women - Healthy Society" have been organized in the regions of the republic, ensuring the participation of more than 500 thousand women and girls every year [27; 56-p]. The Government Commission, which is constantly working on issues of strengthening the health of a healthy generation, women's health, and increasing the level of medical culture in the family, has developed a number of competent state departments and other interested structures with the participation of priority areas for improving medical culture in the family, further strengthening women's health, and the birth and upbringing of a healthy generation. A targeted program of measures to increase the level of education was approved. The program included the tasks of regularly preparing and holding competitions for the titles of "Healthy Family", "Educational Mother", and "Educational Father" every year. It is clear that the development of a number of sports suitable and specific for women in the country, the promotion of physical activity and its integration into the daily life of the local population, and thus the protection of women's health, further strengthening women's responsibility for their own health, and ensuring the birth of healthy children have become one of the priority tasks. The issue of encouraging female athletes was reflected in the resolution of the President of the country No. PD-1315 of April 1, 2010 "On measures to encourage the work of female sports instructors working at children's sports facilities in rural areas," and it was of significant historical significance. In accordance with this Resolution, it was determined to provide a 15 percent additional salary increase to female physical education teachers and tutors working in rural areas[28; 6-p]. At the same time, the document calls for active promotion of sports among young girls in remote villages, the creation of necessary and favorable conditions for young athletes, and the appointment of highly qualified, professionally trained women with extensive experience to work with children and students at youth sports facilities. The issues of attracting highly qualified teaching staff and financially encouraging their work were discussed. It is worth emphasizing that, taking into account the gender issue, a number of practical works have been carried out in the country to promote young women to mass sports. For example, these indicators amounted to 24 percent in 2005, including 22 percent in rural areas, of course. In 2015, 47 percent of girls, including 44.7 percent in rural areas, were regularly involved in sports [29; 1-p]. When viewed at the regional level, girls' participation in sports decreased in four regions in 2015. It was organized in Fergana region - 47.6 percent, in Namangan region - 47.5 percent, in Samarkand and Khorezm regions - 47.4 percent [30; 2-p]. In 2015, 479 students (166 of them girls) participated in 27 sports in 53 international sports competitions held in more than 24 countries with the funds of the Fund. In 2016-2017, it can be seen that sports training aimed at intensifying international and national sports among women, traditionally held in the past, has gradually become more popular. For example, it is worth noting that more than half a million women actively participated in the Women's Spartakiad.

In addition, the "Tomaris Women" sports festivals held in the regions under the auspices of the Republican Women's Committee have gained positive significance with their scope and popularity. The competitions, which aroused great interest, were held at the city, district, and regional levels. Not only working women, but also housewives, were able to participate in them

in a spirit of generosity [33; P.62.]. These reforms clearly demonstrate that the republican government is seriously concerned about the popularization of sports among all segments of the population and is fully supporting and encouraging women's sports. A total of 11,145 mass sports competitions were held within the framework of sports weeks organized in the republic in 2018. About 2 million people, including 732,076 women, participated in these events. In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 25, 2018 "On further improving the system of republican sports competitions among schoolchildren and students", stages 1-2 of youth competitions in 12 sports were held in all districts (cities) of the republic[34; P.33]. In 2018, 1,788 mass sports events were held among different segments of the population of the Samarkand region, attracting more than 257,000 people (including more than 114,000 women and girls). 7,130 people (including 2,765 girls) participated in 131 competitions held within the framework of the "Youth Week", 4,164 people in 178 competitions held within the framework of the "Women and Girls Week", and 6,892 participants in 281 competitions held within the framework of the "Neighborhood and Enlightenment Week". During these weeks, 30,616 people (including 15,941 women) were covered in mass physical education classes organized in districts and cities. Based on the "Calendar of sports and mass physical education events held among all segments of the population in 2019", approved on January 22, 2019, a total of 24 training camps were held this year in 23 Olympic sports and 1 national sport of wrestling. A total of 368 athletes, including 277 boys and 91 girls, participated in the training camps, and 162 sports events in 62 sports were held according to the plan.[35] A total of 115,610 participants were involved in these sports events, of which 45,805 were women. Special attention is paid to the effective organization of propaganda and promotional activities in the implementation of mass physical education exercises. It should be noted that for these purposes, a demonstration of 3-5-minute video clips aimed at promoting mass physical education exercises was launched through the mass media, Internet networks, and especially television, 3 times a day. As a result of efforts to increase the popularity of sports during the period up to this year, the number of students involved in 38,554 sports clubs organized in secondary schools reached 1,161,779.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the government of Uzbekistan, starting from the first days of independence, has paid special attention to supporting and developing youth and women's sports and has implemented measures in this regard. These efforts have helped, first of all, to develop sports among the younger generation and women, who are demonstrating their physical abilities in national and international sports arenas. The popularization of the traditional three-stage sports games - "Universiade", "Perfect Generation" and "Sprouts of Hope" - once every three years is the result of reforms aimed at protecting the health of the population. The regular holding of these sports competitions has gradually become popular, and new young world champions have become known and famous in the sports world. The country's youth actively participate in not only national but also world universities, achieving high results.

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